

Synthesis of Possible Antiparkinsonian Compounds : Part. VIII. Synthesis of N¹-(Nicotinamido-methyl)-N³-aryl-ureas and N¹-{2-(*o*-Methyl-benzimidazolyl)-salicylamido-methyl}-N³-aryl ureas

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Manuscript received 18 November 1974; accepted 5 February 1975

N-(Hydroxymethyl)-nicotinamide/salicylamide and substituted N-aryl-ureas were condensed in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid yielding N¹-(nicotinamido/salicylamido-methyl)-N³-aryl-ureas (I) with a view to testing their antiparkinsonian activity. A part of this study has also been devoted to the synthesis of N¹-{2-(*o*-methyl-benzimidazolyl)-salicylamido-methyl}-N³-aryl-ureas (II) which were synthesised by the condensation of equimolar amounts of N¹-(salicylamidomethyl)-N³-aryl-ureas and chloromethyl benzimidazole in anhydrous acetone and dry potassium carbonate. A few compounds of this series were subjected for their antioxotremorine activity in albino rats of either sex but none of the compounds antagonised the oxotremorine tremor upto 500 mg/kg. intraperitoneally.

THE antiparkinsonian activity of some pyridine and salicylic acid derivatives has been reported by many schools of research¹⁻⁴. In addition, N-aryl-ureas have been found to possess enhanced anti-cholinesterase property⁵. Most of the antiparkinsonian compounds inhibit serum-cholinesterase rather than the tissue-cholinesterase⁶.

Further imidazoline derivatives have been found most effective in antagonising the experimental tremor in mice and the rats⁷. The authors therefore thought it worthwhile to extend the scope and validity of these observations to N¹-(nicotinamido-methyl)-N³-aryl-ureas and N¹-{2-(*o*-methyl-benzimidazolyl)-salicylamido-methyl}-N³-aryl ureas with a view to testing their antiparkinsonian activity.

Experimental

N-(Hydroxymethyl)-nicotinamide/salicylamide
The method of Einhorn *et al.*⁸ was followed.
N¹-(Nicotinamido/salicylamidomethyl)-N³-aryl-ureas
An equimolar amounts of N-(hydroxymethyl)-nicotinamide/salicylamide and N-aryl-ureas were dissolved in minimum quantity of concentrated sulphuric acid (15 ml.). The contents were cooled and stirred for one hour at room temperature. Subsequently the resultant reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. A solid mass was obtained which was filtered and washed repeatedly with water to remove the sulphonated product. It was dried and recrystallised from ethanol. Various compounds thus synthesised are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

N¹-(Nicotinamido/salicylamido-methyl)-N³-aryl-ureas.

Sl. No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	Nicotinamido	H	218—219	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	20.74	20.18
2.	Nicotinamido	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	207—208	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	19.71	19.75
3.	Nicotinamido	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	165	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	19.71	19.85
4.	Nicotinamido	<i>m</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	218	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	17.83	17.31
5.	Nicotinamido	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	188—189	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	22.22	21.94
6.	Nicotinamido	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	185—186	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	19.71	19.34
7.	Salicylamido	H	225—226	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃	14.73	14.22
8.	Salicylamido	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	201—202	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	14.04	14.18
9.	Salicylamido	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	205—206	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	14.04	13.98
10.	Salicylamido	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	140	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	14.04	13.85
11.	Salicylamido	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	120—121	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	13.33	13.25

Note : The solvent used for the recrystallisation was ethanol. Percent yield ranged from 50-65%. All the melting points are corrected.

*N*¹-{2-(*o*-methyl-benzimidazolyl)-salicylamido-methyl}-*N*³-aryl-ureas

A mixture of *N*¹-(Salicylamido-methyl)-*N*³-aryl-urea (0.003 mole), 2-chloromethyl-benzimidazole (0.003 mole) and 0.55 g. of freshly ignited potassium-carbonate in 25 ml. of anhydrous acetone was refluxed on a steam bath for 24 hr. The reaction mixture was then cooled and filtered. Acetone was distilled off and the residue thus obtained, was recrystallised from methanol. The compounds thus synthesised are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2

*N*¹-{2-(*o*-methyl-benzimidazolyl)salicylamido-methyl}-*N*³-aryl ureas

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis	
				Nitrogen	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	H	160	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃	16.86	16.57
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	205-206	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃	16.31	16.14
3.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	120-103	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃	16.31	15.96
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	145-146	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃	16.31	16.01
5.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	85-86	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₄	15.50	15.49

Note:—All the compounds were recrystallised from methanol. The yield ranged from 40-50%.

Pharmacology

The compound Nos. 3, 5 and 11 of the Table 1 were screened for their anti-oxotremorine activity in albino rats of either sex.

Method

The compound under investigation was macerated with an equal amount of gum-acacia and distilled water. The suspension of the test compound was administered intraperitoneally to the rats (300 mg/kg). After one hour, oxotremorine (5 mg/kg) was injected to the animals. This dose of oxotremorine has been found to cause tremors and salivation in untreated animals. The rats were then observed for the occurrence of tremors. None of the compounds was found to inhibit the tremor significantly.

Acknowledgement

Gratitude is extended to Prof. R. B. Arora, Head, Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi for his assistance in screening the compounds. We are also grateful to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a senior research fellowship to one of them (V.K.P.).

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